

Title

Genetic performance profile and its relationship with the incidence and severity of musculoskeletal injuries in non-professional football players

Head title

Genetic profile and sports injuries

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to investigate the association between muscle performance-related genetic profile and the incidence, severity, and recurrence of musculoskeletal injuries in non-professional football players. Additionally, it explored sex-related differences to inform personalized prevention and rehabilitation strategies. A longitudinal descriptive study was conducted with 99 non-professional football players during the 2021/2022 season. DNA was extracted from buccal swabs and genotyped using single nucleotide primer extension (SNPE) for six polymorphisms: AMPD1 (rs17602729), ACE (rs4646994), ACTN3 (rs1815739), CKM (rs8111989), and MLCK (rs2849757 and rs2700352). A Total Genotype Score (TGS) was calculated to assess polygenic potential. Injury data were collected following international consensus guidelines, and only non-traumatic football-related injuries were included. Statistical analyses included chi-square tests, logistic regression, and Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves analysis. The ACTN3 TT genotype was associated with greater injury severity, while the ACE D allele, CKM GG, MLCK AA, and ACTN3 CC genotypes were linked to lower muscle damage. A TGS below the threshold was associated with higher injury risk, except for muscle injuries, where the opposite pattern was observed. TGS showed predictive capacity for injury recurrence in both sexes, with stronger associations in females. These findings suggest that the genetic profile of muscle performance may help identify athletes at greater risk of injury and inform personalized training and recovery strategies. Sex-specific genetic influences highlight the importance of individualized approaches in sports injury prevention.

Key words: Polymorphism; Total Genotype Score; Injuries, Soccer, Gender Characteristics.

1. Introduction

Injuries in sports represent a major constraint on athletic performance and the competitive continuity of football players, impacting not only their physical health but also their professional trajectories [1]. The overall injury incidence in professional football is estimated at approximately 8.1 injuries per 1000 hours of exposure. Although most injuries are classified as mild to moderate in severity, the lower limbs are disproportionately affected, with muscular and tendinous injuries being the most [2,3].

Recent research underscores that the psychological consequences of sports injuries can be as debilitating as the physical damage itself. Injured athletes frequently experience a range of emotional responses—including anxiety, depression, anger, and frustration—that may significantly hinder their rehabilitation and return to performance [4]. These psychological reactions are often influenced by the severity of the injury, the athlete's coping mechanisms, and the support systems available during recovery. Studies have shown that mental health symptoms such as depressive mood and anxiety are prevalent among injured elite athletes, and these symptoms can persist long after physical recovery [4,5].

The occurrence of injuries is influenced by a complex interplay of biochemical, histological, anthropometric, physiological, psychological, and genetic factors. Notably, genetic components may account for over 60% of individual variability in injury susceptibility [6].

Genetic polymorphisms regulate key biological functions such as muscle fiber composition, energy metabolism, and recovery capacity, all of which may significantly influence injury risk [7,8]. For example, the c.1729C>T polymorphism in the alpha-actinin-3 gene (*ACTN3*) has been associated with strength and speed performance [9], while the I/D polymorphism in the angiotensin-converting enzyme (*ACE*) gene is linked to aerobic capacity [10]. Recently, it has

been shown that the c.34C>T polymorphism in the adenosine monophosphate deaminase 1 (AMPD1) gene may influence muscle fatigue resistance and energy metabolism, potentially affecting injury susceptibility in athletes [11]. Similarly, variants in the muscle creatine kinase (CKM) gene have been associated with muscle contraction efficiency and recovery capacity [12], while polymorphisms in the myosin light chain kinase (MLCK) gene are implicated in muscle fiber regulation and adaptation to mechanical stress [13].

Despite growing interest in the genetic basis of injury susceptibility, the field still faces significant limitations. While several polymorphisms have been associated with traits relevant to injury risk, the current body of evidence remains fragmented and often lacks replication across diverse athletic populations. Many studies are limited by small sample sizes, heterogeneous methodologies, and inconsistent phenotype definitions, which complicate the translation of genetic findings into practical applications. Moreover, the interaction between genetic variants and environmental factors—such as training load, recovery strategies, and psychological stress—is still poorly understood. This gap underscores the need for integrative models that combine genetic, physiological, and psychological data to better predict injury risk and guide personalized prevention strategies. Advancing this field will require large-scale, multidisciplinary studies with robust designs and longitudinal follow-up to validate genetic markers and clarify their role in injury mechanisms.

Therefore, the purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between the genetic profile associated with muscle performance and the incidence, severity, and recurrence of musculoskeletal injuries in non-professional soccer players. By analyzing a panel of relevant polymorphisms, we aimed to explore how genetic predisposition may influence injury risk and recovery dynamics. Additionally, we sought to examine sex-related differences in genetic associations, with the goal of informing more personalized approaches to injury prevention and rehabilitation in amateur football contexts.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Participants

This longitudinal descriptive study analyzed 99 non-professional football players in Spain during 2021/2022 season. The characteristics of this cohort are presented in Table 1.

Variable	Total	Male	Female	p-value
Age, mean (SD)	22.82 (5.15)	22.43 (5.32)	23.26 (4.98)	0.43
Number of injuries, mean (SD)	1.75 (1.3)	1.7 (0.77)	1.81 (1.69)	0.726
Injury incidence (per 1000 h), mean (SD)	9.67 (10.65)	5.42 (2.65)	14.06 (13.7)	0.001
Playing position				0.656
Goalkeepers	10 (6.8%)	5 (50%)	5 (50%)	
Defenders	29 (19.7%)	16 (55.2%)	13 (44.8%)	
Midfielders	26 (17.7%)	16 (61.5%)	10 (38.5%)	
Forwards	31 (21.1%)	14 (45.2%)	17 (54.8%)	

Table 1. Non-professional football players' demographic characteristics by sex. Continuous variables are presented as mean (SD), categorical variables as n (%). P-values were calculated using t-test for continuous variables and chi-squared test for categorical variables.

Participants were eligible for inclusion if they met the following conditions: i) non-professional football players under contract with the first team of a football club; ii) consistent participation in training sessions and official matches throughout the season with the same club; and iii) engagement in regular exercise training sessions lasting more than 1 hour, at least 3 days per week, during the 6 months preceding the study. Participants were excluded if they met any of

the following conditions: i) sustained only contact-related injuries during the season; ii) experienced disabling injuries that prevented participation in football training or matches within the 6 months prior to the study onset; or iii) were classified as professional football players.

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their inclusion in the study. The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the University Francisco de Vitoria (approval code: UFV 32/2020) and conducted in accordance with the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki (1964), as revised in 2013. All football players included in the study were assigned a coded identifier to ensure confidentiality and data protection.

2.2 Desoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) sample and genotyping

Samples were collected during the 2021/2022 season using SARSTEDT buccal swabs and were stored under refrigeration until genotyping. DNA extraction was performed at VIVOLabs (Madrid, Spain) using an automated QIAcube system (QIAGEN, Venlo, The Netherlands), yielding DNA concentrations of 25–40 ng/ml. DNA was stored in solution at a volume of 100 µL at –20°C until genotyping.

The *ACE* I/D (rs4646994), *ACTN3* c.1729C>T (rs1815739), *AMPD1* c.34C>T (rs17602729), *CKM* c.*800A>G (rs8111989), and *MLCK* c.37885C>A (rs28497577) and c.49C>T (rs2700352) polymorphisms were genotyped using single nucleotide primer extension (SNPE) with the SNaPshot Multiplex Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA). Reaction products were analyzed by capillary electrophoresis on an ABI3500 system (Applied Biosystems, CA, USA), and bioinformatic analyses were performed with GeneMapper 5.0 software (Applied Biosystems, CA, USA).

2.3 Injury data collection

Individual exposure of each player during training sessions and official matches was systematically recorded by the respective football clubs as part of their routine workload monitoring throughout the season. This study included all players who sustained injuries with a special focus on non-traumatic, non-contact injuries documented by the club's medical staff during the 2021/2022 season.

To be eligible for analysis, injuries had to be directly related to football activity, occurring either during training or competition. Injuries resulted from collisions with other players or external objects were excluded, as such events are unlikely to be influenced by genetic factors.

Injury data were collected by the team at each club recorded using a standardized paper-based questionnaire. This form was completed whenever a player required medical attention and subsequently submitted to the head of the club's medical department. Medical personnel were instructed to report any injury defined as 'any physical complaint sustained by a player as a result of a football match or training session, regardless of the need for medical attention or time loss from football activities.' The data collection adhered to the international consensus statement on injury surveillance in football, as recommended by the Fédération Internationale de Football Association (FIFA) and the Union of European Football Associations (UEFA) [14–16]. Injuries were categorized into the following etiological groups; i) muscle fiber ruptures, ii) tendon or /joint injuries, iii) severe injuries (defined as those resulting in absence >28 days), and iv) recurrent injuries. All injuries were classified according to a modified version of the Orchard Sports Injury Classification System [17].

2.4 Genotypic potential

The combined influence of the six studied polymorphisms was calculated using a Total Genotype Score (TGS), following the procedure described by Williams and Folland [18]. Each genotype was assigned a Genotype Score (GS) of 2 for the “protective” genotype, 1 for the heterozygous genotype, and 0 for the “worst” genotype [11]. The score of GS of all genotypes was transformed to a 0–100 arbitrary units (a.u) scale to facilitate interpretation, namely the total genotype score (TGS), as follows:

$$TGS = (GS_{AMPD1} + GS_{ACE} + GS_{ACTN3} + GS_{CKM} + GS_{MLCK37885} + GS_{MLCK49}) \times 100/12$$

As previously indicated [18], a TGS of 100 a.u. represents a “perfect protective” profile and a TGS of 0 a.u. would be the “worst protective” possible profile for muscle and tendon or ligament injuries when all GSs have a score of 0 a.u. Finally, the TGS distribution between non-injury and injury characteristics was assessed.

2.5 Statistical analysis

All analyses were performed using R software (v.4.4.1). The full script is available at: https://github.com/Pabloph9/TFM_Genetic_Profile_Muscle_Injuries .

Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) was assessed for all SNPs using the χ^2 test. Genotype frequencies were compared between injured and non-injured players using the χ^2 test with a fixed $\alpha = 0.05$. Genotypic frequencies were also compared across different injury etiologies using the same test. The ability of the TGS to discriminate between injured (0 = no, 1 = yes) and non-injured players, as well as across different etiologies, musculoskeletal injuries (0 = no, 1 = yes), tendon/joint injuries (0 = no, 1 = yes), severe injuries >28 days (0 = no, 1 = yes), and recurrent injuries (0 = no, 1 = yes), was evaluated using Receiver Operating Characteristic

(ROC) curves [19]. The area under the ROC curve (AUC) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) was calculated. Finally, a binary logistic regression model was applied to examine the relationship between TGS and injury etiology.

3. Results

The polymorphisms analyzed met the HWE (all $p > 0.05$). The database included a total of 147 injuries; 74 in male and 73 in female non-professional football players. The characteristics of the injuries recorded and analyzed during the 2021/2022 season are presented in Table 2, for whom the average muscle performance TGS was slightly higher in female (66.4 ± 10.8 a.u.) compared to male (63.8 ± 10.2 a.u.).

Injury category	Total (n)	Male (n, %)	Female (n, %)
Total injuries	147	74 (50.3%)	73 (49.7%)
Muscle injuries	39	23 (59.0%)	16 (41.0%)
Joint/tendon injuries	58	27 (46.6%)	31 (53.4%)
Severe injuries (>28 days)	26	16 (61.5%)	10 (38.5%)
Recurrent injuries	17	8 (47.1%)	9 (52.9%)

Table 2. Distribution and characteristics of all injuries recorded during the 2021/2022 season in non-professional football players. Values represent the total number of cases and the percentage by sex.

Subsequently, individual genotype frequencies were analyzed to explore potential differences in distribution and assess whether any polymorphisms showed differential trends according to sex. Variations were observed in ACTN3, CKM, and MLCK C49T, where female exhibited a higher frequency of genotypes associated with higher genetic scores (Table 3).

Name	Gene	Polymorphisms	Genetic score	Males n (%)	Females n (%)
<i>ACTN3</i>	α -actinin 3	rs1815739	2 = CC	33 (30.6%)	22 (30.1%)
			1 = CT	50 (46.3%)	42 (57.5%)
			0 = TT	25 (23.1%)	9 (12.3%)
<i>ACE</i>	Angiotensin- converting enzyme	rs4340	2 = DD	39 (36.1%)	32 (43.8%)
			1 = ID	57 (52.8%)	30 (41.1%)
			0 = II	12 (11.1%)	11 (15.1%)
<i>AMPD1</i>	Adenosine Monophosphate Deaminase 1	rs17602729	2 = CC	80 (74.1%)	65 (89.0%)
			1 = CT	27 (25.0%)	7 (9.6%)
			0 = TT	1 (0.9%)	1 (1.4%)
<i>MLCKC37885A</i>	Creatine kinase light chain	C37885A	2 = CC	87 (80.6%)	59 (80.8%)
			1 = CA	20 (18.5%)	14 (19.2%)
			0 = AA	1 (0.9%)	0 (0.0%)
<i>MLCKC49T</i>	Creatine kinase light chain	C49T	2 = CC	67 (62.0%)	57 (78.1%)
			1 = CT	35 (32.4%)	16 (21.9%)
			0 = TT	6 (5.6%)	0 (0.0%)
<i>CKM</i>	Muscle creatine kinase	A/G	2 = AA	6 (5.6%)	9 (12.3%)

1 = AG	44 (40.7%)	25 (34.2%)
0 = GG	58 (53.7%)	39 (53.4%)

Table 3. Distribution of genetic polymorphisms in muscle performance-related genes, differentiated by sex.

3.1 Muscle injuries

First, the occurrence of muscle injuries was analyzed. Athletes who sustained a muscle injury presented higher mean TGS values (67.11 a.u.) relative to those without injuries (63.54 a.u.). This difference was more pronounced in females, in whom injured players showed significantly higher TGS (71.93 a.u.) compared with non-injured (64.57 a.u.) ($p = 0.01387$).

From the total of 147 injuries recorded, 39 corresponded to muscle injuries. In females, TGS demonstrated a strong predictive capacity for muscle injury ($p = 0.0041$) (Figure 1A). In contrast, the ROC curve did not reach statistical significance in male ($p = 0.7966$) (Figure 1B). Binary logistic regression revealed that a TGS above 66.23 a.u. was associated with more than a fivefold higher risk of sustaining a muscle injury, exclusively in females (OR = 5.778; $p = 0.014$). Genotype distribution did not show significant differences at the individual level, and no clear trends were observed (Table 4).

Figure 1. ROC curves for the performance Total Genetic Score (TGS) and muscle injury in female (A) and male (B) athletes. The area under the curve (AUC) with the 95% confidence interval (CI) is displayed in each panel.

Gene	Sex	Genotype	Not muscle injured	Muscle injured	P value	
<i>ACE</i>	Female	0 = II	8 (19.0%)	2 (12.5%)	0.6821	
		1 = ID	18 (42.9%)	6 (37.5%)		
		2 = DD	16 (38.1%)	8 (50.0%)		
	Male	0 = II	3 (9.1%)	5 (21.7%)		0.2891
		1 = ID	18 (54.5%)	13 (56.5%)		
		2 = DD	12 (36.4%)	5 (21.7%)		
<i>ACTN3</i>	Female	0 = TT	6 (14.3%)	1 (6.2%)	0.6900	
		1 = CT	23 (54.8%)	10 (62.5%)		
		2 = CC	13 (31.0%)	5 (31.2%)		
	Male	0 = TT	7 (21.2%)	4 (17.4%)		0.8869
		1 = CT	15 (45.5%)	10 (43.5%)		
		2 = CC	11 (33.3%)	9 (39.1%)		

<i>AMPDI</i>	Female	0 = TT	1 (2.4%)	0 (0.0%)	0.6777
		1 = CT	3 (7.1%)	2 (12.5%)	
		2 = CC	38 (90.5%)	14 (87.5%)	
	Male	1 = CT	10 (30.3%)	10 (43.5%)	0.4661
		2 = CC	23 (69.7%)	13 (56.5%)	
<i>CKM</i>	Female	0 = AA	23 (54.8%)	7 (43.8%)	0.5444
		1 = GA	12 (28.6%)	7 (43.8%)	
		2 = GG	7 (16.7%)	2 (12.5%)	
	Male	0 = AA	21 (63.6%)	10 (43.5%)	0.3276
		1 = GA	11 (33.3%)	12 (52.2%)	
		2 = GG	1 (3.0%)	1 (4.3%)	
<i>MLCKC37885A</i>	Female	1 = CA	10 (23.8%)	4 (25.0%)	1.0000
		2 = AA	32 (76.2%)	12 (75.0%)	
	Male	1 = CA	5 (15.2%)	5 (21.7%)	
		2 = AA	28 (84.8%)	18 (78.3%)	
<i>MLCKC49T</i>	Female	1 = TC	9 (21.4%)	2 (12.5%)	0.6888
		2 = CC	33 (78.6%)	14 (87.5%)	
	Male	1 = TC	8 (24.2%)	9 (39.1%)	
		2 = CC	25 (75.8%)	14 (60.9%)	

Table 4. Distribution of genotypic frequencies according to muscle injury status in non-professional male and female football players. Comparisons between genotypic distributions were performed using the Chi-square test.

3.2 Joint/tendon injuries

A total of 58 injuries were classified as joint or tendon injuries. Overall, an opposite pattern relative to muscle injuries was observed: injured players showed a lower mean TGS (62.94 a.u.) relative to non-injured players (66.67 a.u.). This effect was again more pronounced in females, in whom players with joint injuries had lower TGS values (63.02 a.u.) than those without injuries (70.87 a.u.) ($p = 0.007081$).

ROC analysis revealed significant predictive capacity only in female non-professional football players ($p < 0.001$) (Figure 2A). In male, the ROC curve was not significant, with values close to random ($p = 0.9151$) (Figure 2B). Logistic regression confirmed that female with a TGS below the threshold of 66.23 a.u. had a sevenfold higher risk of sustaining a joint/tendon injury compared with those above the threshold (OR = 7.00; 95% CI: 2.25–24.51; $p = 0.0013$). Genotype distribution for joint and tendon injuries did not show significant associations in any of the polymorphisms analyzed (Table 5).

Figure 2. ROC curve of performance TGS as a predictor of joint/tendon injury in non-professional female (A) and male (B) football players. The area under the curve (AUC) with the 95% confidence interval (CI) is displayed in each panel.

Gene	Sex	Genotype	Not joint/tendon injured	Joint/tendon Injured	p value	
<i>ACE</i>	Female	0 = II	6 (23.1%)	4 (12.9%)	0.5421	
		1 = ID	9 (34.6%)	14 (45.2%)		
		2 = DD	11 (42.3%)	13 (41.9%)		
	Male	0 = II	6 (20.7%)	2 (7.4%)		0.3197
		1 = ID	14 (48.3%)	17 (63%)		
		2 = DD	9 (31%)	8 (29.6%)		
<i>ACTN3</i>	Female	0 = TT	2 (7.7%)	5 (16.1%)	0.6127	
		1 = CT	15 (57.7%)	17 (54.8%)		
		2 = CC	9 (34.6%)	9 (29%)		
	Male	0 = TT	6 (20.7%)	5 (18.5%)		0.8782
		1 = CT	12 (41.4%)	13 (48.1%)		
		2 = CC	11 (37.9%)	9 (33.3%)		
<i>AMPD1</i>	Female	0 = TT	1 (3.8%)	0 (0%)	0.4199	
		1 = CT	3 (11.5%)	2 (6.5%)		
		2 = CC	22 (84.6%)	29 (93.5%)		
	Male	1 = CT	12 (41.4%)	8 (29.6%)		0.5236
		2 = CC	17 (58.6%)	19 (70.4%)		
<i>CKM</i>	Female	0 = AA	11 (42.3%)	18 (58.1%)	0.4902	
		1 = GA	10 (38.5%)	9 (29%)		
		2 = GG	5 (19.2%)	4 (12.9%)		
	Male	0 = AA	14 (48.3%)	17 (63%)		0.5201

<i>MLCKC37885A</i>		1 = GA	14 (48.3%)	9 (33.3%)	
		2 = GG	1 (3.4%)	1 (3.7%)	
	Female	1 = CA	5 (19.2%)	9 (29%)	0.5841
		2 = AA	21 (80.8%)	22 (71%)	
<i>MLCKC49T</i>	Male	1 = CA	7 (24.1%)	3 (11.1%)	0.3562
		2 = AA	22 (75.9%)	24 (88.9%)	
	Female	1 = TC	4 (15.4%)	7 (22.6%)	0.7273
		2 = CC	22 (84.6%)	24 (77.4%)	
	Male	1 = TC	9 (31%)	8 (29.6%)	1
		2 = CC	20 (69%)	19 (70.4%)	

Table 5. Distribution of genotypic frequencies according to joint/tendon injury status in non-professional male and female football players. Comparisons between genotypic distributions were performed using the Chi-square test.

3.3 Injury severity

Injuries lasting more than 28 days were classified as severe, and those below this threshold as non-severe. A total of 88 non-severe injuries and 26 severe injuries were recorded. Overall, mean TGS was higher in non-severe injuries. When stratified by sex, the difference was accentuated in females, with severe injuries showing significantly lower TGS (58.64 a.u.) compared with non-severe injuries (67.59 a.u.) ($p = 0.0337$).

In females, a moderate predictive ability was observed ($p = 0.0242$) (Figure 3A). In contrast, in males, TGS did not show significant predictive capacity ($p = 0.1614$) (Figure 3B). Logistic regression revealed

that female with a TGS below 66.23 a.u. had more than a fivefold higher risk of sustaining severe injuries relative to those above this threshold (OR = 5.692; 95% CI: 1.299–39.805; $p = 0.0364$).

Figure 3. ROC curve of performance TGS as a predictor of injury severity in non-professional female (A) and male (B) football players. The area under the curve (AUC) with the 95% confidence interval (CI) is displayed in each panel.

The genotype distribution showed significant differences for ACTN3 ($p < 0.001$). Players with severe injuries had a higher frequency of the TT genotype (50%) compared with players without severe injuries (4.2%). Conversely, the optimal CC genotype was more frequent in players without severe injuries (35.4%) than in those with severe injuries (10%) (Table 6).

Gene	Sex	Genotype	Not severe	Severe	p value
ACE	Female	0 = II	8 (16.7%)	2 (20%)	0.7231
		1 = ID	21 (43.8%)	3 (30%)	
		2 = DD	19 (39.6%)	5 (50%)	
	Male	0 = II	7 (17.5%)	1 (6.2%)	0.542
		1 = ID	21 (52.5%)	10 (62.5%)	
		2 = DD	12 (30%)	5 (31.2%)	

<i>ACTN3</i>	Female	0 = TT	2 (4.2%)	5 (50%)	< 0.001
		1 = CT	29 (60.4%)	4 (40%)	
		2 = CC	17 (35.4%)	1 (10%)	
	Male	0 = TT	8 (20%)	3 (18.8%)	0.7153
		1 = CT	19 (47.5%)	6 (37.5%)	
		2 = CC	13 (32.5%)	7 (43.8%)	
<i>AMPD1</i>	Female	0 = TT	1 (2.1%)	0 (0%)	0.3415
		1 = CT	3 (6.2%)	2 (20%)	
		2 = CC	44 (91.7%)	8 (80%)	
	Male	1 = CT	16 (40%)	4 (25%)	0.4535
		2 = CC	24 (60%)	12 (75%)	
<i>CKM</i>	Female	0 = AA	28 (58.3%)	2 (20%)	0.0726
		1 = GA	13 (27.1%)	6 (60%)	
		2 = GG	7 (14.6%)	2 (20%)	
	Male	0 = AA	24 (60%)	7 (43.8%)	0.2723
		1 = GA	14 (35%)	9 (56.2%)	
		2 = GG	2 (5%)	0 (0%)	
<i>MLCKC37885A</i>	Female	1 = CA	13 (27.1%)	1 (10%)	0.4579
		2 = AA	35 (72.9%)	9 (90%)	
	Male	1 = CA	8 (20%)	2 (12.5%)	0.7827
		2 = AA	32 (80%)	14 (87.5%)	
<i>MLCKC49T</i>	Female	1 = TC	7 (14.6%)	4 (40%)	0.1551

	2 = CC	41 (85.4%)	6 (60%)	
Male	1 = TC	14 (35%)	3 (18.8%)	0.3826
	2 = CC	26 (65%)	13 (81.2%)	

Table 6. Distribution of genotypic frequencies according to joint/tendon injury status in non-professional male and female football players. Comparisons between genotypic distributions were performed using the Chi-square test.

3.4 Association with previous injury

To assess the risk of injury recurrence, the association between performance TGS and the occurrence of recurrent injuries was analyzed. Only 17 recurrent injuries were recorded. Mean TGS values were lower in recurrent injuries. When stratified by sex, this pattern was consistent in both males and females, although the differences were more pronounced in males ($p = 0.0036$) relative to females ($p = 0.0183$).

Performance TGS showed significant predictive capacity in both sexes. In females, the predictive ability was significant ($p = 0.0314$) (Figure 4A), while in males, it was even stronger ($p = 0.0056$) (Figure 4B). Binary logistic regressions yielded promising results, indicated that athletes with a TGS below the threshold of 59.43 a.u. were at higher risk of recurrent injuries in both sexes, with a higher magnitude of risk in females (OR = 12.091; 95% CI: 2.512–89.542; $p = 0.0042$) compared with males (OR = 9.8; 95% CI: 1.571–190.842; $p = 0.0395$).

Figure 4. ROC curve of performance TGS as a predictor of recurrent injury in female non-professional football players (A) and male (B). The area under the curve (AUC) with the 95% confidence interval (CI) is displayed in each panel.

Genotype distribution showed significant results in both sexes. In males, ACE ($p = 0.0073$) presented a higher frequency of the optimal genotype (33.3%) and a lower frequency of the least favorable genotype (8.3%) among players without recurrences. In females, several genes showed significant associations, including ACE ($p = 0.0067$), ACTN3 ($p = 0.0177$), CKM ($p = 0.0492$), and MLCK37885A ($p < 0.001$) (Table 7). In all cases, genotypes classified as optimal were more frequent in players without recurrences.

Gene	Sex	Genotype	No previous lesion	Previous lesion	p value
ACE	Female	0 = II	10 (20.4%)	0 (0%)	0.0067
		1 = ID	16 (32.7%)	8 (88.9%)	
		2 = DD	23 (46.9%)	1 (11.1%)	
	Male	0 = II	4 (8.3%)	4 (50%)	0.0073
		1 = ID	28 (58.3%)	3 (37.5%)	

		2 = DD	16 (33.3%)	1 (12.5%)	
ACTN3	Female	0 = TT	7 (14.3%)	0 (0%)	0.0177
		1 = CT	24 (49%)	9 (100%)	
		2 = CC	18 (36.7%)	0 (0%)	
	Male	0 = TT	10 (20.8%)	1 (12.5%)	0.8561
		1 = CT	21 (43.8%)	4 (50%)	
		2 = CC	17 (35.4%)	3 (37.5%)	
AMPD1	Female	0 = TT	1 (2%)	0 (0%)	0.5409
		1 = CT	5 (10.2%)	0 (0%)	
		2 = CC	43 (87.8%)	9 (100%)	
	Male	1 = CT	16 (33.3%)	4 (50%)	0.6084
		2 = CC	32 (66.7%)	4 (50%)	
CKM	Female	0 = AA	22 (44.9%)	8 (88.9%)	0.0492
		1 = GA	18 (36.7%)	1 (11.1%)	
		2 = GG	9 (18.4%)	0 (0%)	
	Male	0 = AA	25 (52.1%)	6 (75%)	0.4559
		1 = GA	21 (43.8%)	2 (25%)	
		2 = GG	2 (4.2%)	0 (0%)	
MLCKC37885A	Female	1 = CA	7 (14.3%)	7 (77.8%)	< 0.001
		2 = AA	42 (85.7%)	2 (22.2%)	
	Male	1 = CA	7 (14.6%)	3 (37.5%)	0.2854
		2 = AA	41 (85.4%)	5 (62.5%)	
MLCKC49T	Female	1 = TC	10 (20.4%)	1 (11.1%)	0.8482

	2 = CC	39 (79.6%)	8 (88.9%)	
Male	1 = TC	12 (25%)	5 (62.5%)	0.0854
	2 = CC	36 (75%)	3 (37.5%)	

Table 7. Distribution of genotypic frequencies according to recurrence of previous injuries in non-professional male and female football players. Comparisons between genotypic distributions were performed using the Chi-square test.

4. Discussion

In the present study, a TGS model of muscle performance was developed based on six genetic polymorphisms related to muscle function. These included AMPD1 (rs17602729), ACE (rs4646994), ACTN3 (rs1815739), CKM (rs8111989), and MLCK (rs2849757 and rs2700352), to assess their association with sports injuries, as previously documented in the literature (8). Although numerous studies have explored the genetics of sports performance, most have focused on professional football players and have not considered potential physiological and genetic differences between male and female.

Regarding muscle injuries, the results do not allow for a meaningful analysis at the individual genetic level. However, the effects observed in the ROC curve and logistic regression appear sufficient to explain the risk of injury at a polygenic level. Previous studies have shown that females have a higher proportion of type I fibers, which are more resistant to fatigue, and a lower proportion of type II fibers, which are more explosive but also more susceptible to eccentric contraction-induced injuries (15). These characteristics explain their lower fatigability during prolonged efforts. In addition, during endurance exercise, females tend to use lipids as

an energy source compared to male, who rely more on glucose (16). However, when combined with genotypes associated with greater power or glycolytic capacity (such as the CC genotype of *ACTN3* or the CC genotype of *AMPD1*), a functional imbalance may arise. Several studies suggest that certain genetic variations may elicit different responses to muscle damage depending on the type of contraction and the demands placed on the musculoskeletal system (17). In this sense, a profile considered “optimal” for power may predispose to muscle injuries if these structural properties are not adequately balanced to support the workload.

For joint injuries, the sex differences observed may be explained by specific adaptations of the muscle–tendon complex (MTC). *McMahon et al.* reported that females show a lower adaptive response of the MTC to high loads compared with males. This difference may limit the functional properties of the MTC in females, influencing joint stability (18). In contrast, in males, the adaptive response of the MTC to high loads may reduce the impact of these effects.

In sports, it is important not only to assess the incidence of injuries but also their severity, as this directly affects rehabilitation and the progression of players. Severe injuries are known to require longer recovery periods and carry a higher risk of recurrence (19).

The c.1729C>T polymorphism of the *ACTN3* gene is associated with two genetic variants: the CC genotype, linked to superior performance in power activities (8,20), and the TT genotype, which results in complete deficiency of the *ACTN3* protein. The TT genotype is less frequent among elite athletes, suggesting a reduced capacity for strength and speed activities (21). Furthermore, this genotype has been associated with increased injury severity, as confirmed by recent research (22). *Massidda et al.* showed that the absence of alpha-actinin-3 leads to prolonged recovery periods, directly impacting injury severity.

To explain potential sex differences, it has been demonstrated that females present anatomical and biomechanical characteristics such as a greater range of foot movement and increased

ligamentous laxity, which may increase the risk of acute injuries (23). Moreover, females are known to have a higher incidence of anterior cruciate ligament injuries, possibly related to neuromuscular control deficits specific to females (24).

With respect to recurrent injuries, the *ACE* gene appears to be one of the main contributors to the discriminative ability of the TGS. The I/D polymorphism suggests that players carrying the D allele may have a lower predisposition to muscle injuries and faster recovery, which is associated with greater *ACE* activity modulating the inflammatory response and muscle damage after intense exercise (25). The *CKM* polymorphism showed that the GG genotype is more frequent in power athletes. This genotype has been linked to a lower creatine kinase (*CK*) response after intense exercise, suggesting a potential protective effect against exercise-induced muscle damage (26). Regarding the *MLCK* gene, which regulates non-skeletal muscle contraction and vascular permeability during inflammation (27), the C37885A polymorphism was associated with reduced force-generating capacity and increased muscle fatigue in CC individuals. Conversely, the AA genotype showed a lower incidence of these negative effects, as well as greater preservation of muscle strength (28).

While this study offers an innovative approach, it has several limitations. The sample size was limited, particularly in the analysis of recurrent injuries, where the limited number of cases resulted in wide and unreliable confidence intervals. Although autosomal polymorphisms should not show systematic differences between sexes, the slight variations observed in the descriptive analysis are most likely due to the reduced sample size, which may have led to small differences in allele frequencies between male and female. It would be useful to consider some intrinsic training characteristics that may have influenced the results. Furthermore, exploring new genetic variants could help complement the findings. It is important to highlight that this analysis is pioneering in its field, and unresolved issues remain, such as the possible functional imbalance in muscle injuries. It is also necessary to investigate the interaction of genetic

variants with environmental and nutritional factors, and to develop new predictive tools to more accurately identify athletes at risk.

5. Conclusions

Previous studies have extensively explored the influence of genetics on athletic performance and susceptibility to injury. However, this study stands out as the first to show that the genetic profile of muscle performance is associated with the incidence and severity of musculoskeletal injuries in non-professional soccer players.

In addition, significant differences were observed according to sex, suggesting that certain physiological and genetic factors could explain a greater susceptibility to injuries and relapses in females. In particular, the TT genotype of the ACTN3 polymorphism was associated with an increased risk of serious injuries and longer recovery times, demonstrating its potential as a genetic marker in the field of sports prevention.

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Conflict of interest declaration

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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